

Social Capital, Family Support and Religion Impact over Youth Civic Engagement: Study on Undergraduate Students Japan

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ABSTRACT: The research focused to assess impact of social capital, family support and religion on civic engagement using deductive approach. The sample for study was collected from Japanese educated youth using online google form survey. Questionnaire was linked with different social media platform. The hypothesis testing was conducted total 209 samples, using multi-regression with cross-sectional data. The association between bonding social capital and civic engagement was positive and significant while bridging social capital was reported insignificant. Results reported that association between family support and civic engagement was positive and significant in Japanese youth context while strong association between religion and civic engagement was reported. This study covers undergraduate students and this is main limitation of the study. For further research comparative study of undergraduate and graduate study is suggested.

Key words: Social Capital, Family Support, Religion and Civic Engagement.

[Introduction](#)
[Methodology](#)
[Results](#)
[Discussion](#)
[Conclusion](#)
[References](#)

1. Introduction

In the era of information technology and ease of socioeconomic transformation, the developed societies are facing social inequality that enhance new challenges which lead huge risk and uncertainty almost all segment of population. Lifetime employment stability along with a precarious types of engagement with work, retrenchment of the state policies related to welfare of inhabitants, besides lack of sustainable social bonds and hitherto are given by social primary groups, pushes up toward to financial and social uncertainties

Beck & Whelan (2009) in their research pin pointed that complexities of life due to industrialization has aggravated the situation further. Unfortunately, social institutions to be relied to provide a sustainable structure and positive connation, change appearance and lose their unifying status. Consequences, individualization of social environmental threats creates space for vulnerability and precarity (Schacter et al.,2022; Misztal & Barbara,2011) which lead toward lack of sharing social and financial constrains to primary and secondary social groups.

During and after covid19, both developed and developing societies are facing different kinds of social and financial constraints which has changed shape of social structure, hence, expectations toward the social workers and philanthropists have increased to support public. However, it was also claimed that as industrialization increased, social interaction of people decreased which lead to decline of social capital in developed society(Putnam,2000). Such perceptions have given space for different ideas to how to deal with social issues by participating formal as well as informal civic engagement (Jalalani et al.,2018). Times Constrain commenced when industrialization increased, made workforce busy and decreased social bonds within society. Lack of social bonds in society lead population toward decline of social capital which major source of close contacts in social system (Jalalani et al.,2019).

Social capital nurtures the social bonds and make healthy and sustainable relationships between individual and social group within society (Jalalani et al.,2018; Allison,2013; Miyamoto,2012). Such social groups step up to work out for social development of society by participating in civic engagement related social activities. Individual's engagement with different social activities depends on support of primary social groups like family member workmate and friends which is the basic of bonding social of individuals as well as social groups. The family members support is major source that encourage individual to participate in social activities for social development society (Lenzi et al.,2012). Individuals' social behavior related to tendency of socialization through primary social institutions while it is also part of cultural setting (Rossi et al.,2016). Some investigator linked individuals' prosocial behaviors with religious values and figured out strong association between religious values and individual's participation in civic engagement related social activities to enhance the social environment to encourage individuals as wells groups to participate social development masses (Storm,2015).

In theoretical perspectives, many studies were conducted in this domain to understand impacts of determinants associated with civic engagement which encouraged individuals as well as social groups to work out for social development within society using different factors (Schacter et al.,2022; Jalalani et al.,2019; Storm,2015 Allison,2013; Miyamoto,2012). However, a rare studies focused over the association between bonding, bridging social capital, family support and religion values involvement to encourage youth participate engagement related social activities for social development in Japanese context. This is a major gap of current research to fill the theoretical as well as context in domain literature. The outcomes of current research may helpful for philanthropist, social workers, domain development professionals and new scholars of domain to work out for social development society.

Theoretical framework and hypothesis development

In a broad-spectrum, people engagement in social activities are considered a step toward participatory and social development of society. Civic engagement makes possible for the less and marginalize section of society to be a part of development. The civic engagement can be divided in two basic ideas, formal and informal. The formal such as, any person of society performs any activity which is related to political activism including joining political party, voting and so on. Such kinds of social activities are assumed formal

civic engagement while community service, volunteering, activism and advocacy related social activities are through be informal civic engagement.

The civic engagement is a multi-perspectives concept. Hence, it has been assessed in different ways by linking several factors in previous studies (Fernandez et al.,2022; Jalalani and Shah,2019; Garcia et al.,2016; Akman & Amna,2012). In the previous studies a sufficient work has been done regarding the association between social capital and civic engagement while family support and impact of religion and its values were overlook in this context. To fill this lacuna, the current study proposes to extend the previous analysis by assessing impact of social capital, family support and impact of religion on civic engagement.

Association between social capital and civic engagement

Assessing the tendency of social relationship between individual and groups and group to group is main domain of social scientists. In this regard, different concept was tested mainstreaming the issue. The Granovetter,(1973) given concept of ties and pointed toward strong and weak ties in society while this concept focused over different social groups. With the little difference later, Putnam, (2000) given idea of social connection in term social networking in society. There was not much difference between social ties and social networking because idea was under umbrella of bridging and bonding ties. However, major issue was that how to deal with individual representation in social system, to deal with issue, concept of bridging and bonding social included for further investigation. In terms of generosity, concept was assessed with formal and informal social engagement.

In the both ideas, several studies were conducted to understand impact of social capital on civic engagement. Level of civic engagement depends on tendency of social capital like it may lack of social capital in urban level as compared to small town and rural, so level of individual's in civic engagement related to level social capital (Besser, 2009). A recent study pointed that level and developing social capital and participating in social activities related age of social actor and youth population more active as compared to middle and senior citizens (Kim & Kim,2021). By enhancing idea, study has reported that higher amounts of social capital have more likely to engage social activities to support needy segment of society. Another study also figured out similar finding by measuring impact of impact of bonding social capital and formal civic engagement. Study assessed offline and online civic engagement among youth and reported that bonding social capital had impact on political engagement (Ferrucci et al.,2022).

Association between family and civic engagement

The civic engagement is millstone of social development of masses. Different theories pointed that civic related activities in society contributes high amount of wellbeing and positive and social development among youth which very important for community and lager civil society (Eriksan,1974; Baltes, 1987; Bobek et al.,2009). Actually civic behaviors stand with contextual aspects like, what types of social environment the individual is lived and avail opportunities and what kind of support help him to take action for development of society (Youniss and Levine,2009). In the social environment, so many individuals' role actions can impact on attitude of person which of them very common are role of family and

friends. That are considered primary source of socialization. Similarly, theory of development of assets, revealed that civic engagement nurture when individual get higher level of psychological and other related support from family and communities members, have more likely to do work out for development community and society at broader level (Benson and Syvertsen, 2011). Hence, family is a primary social institute which help to nurture social behavior and attitude to steps up for development society. In context of family, literature pointed that engagement any family member in social activities, leads youth toward be active in civic engagement to enhance social development of community as well as society (Rossi et al.,2016). In this link, a study was conducted among new immigrant's youth in Canada, study reported that parents' prosocial behavior has impact on their young children over informal civic engagement and rare formal civic engagement behavior was reported among new immigrants' youth in Canadian context (Livianna et al.,2008).

Association between religion and civic engagement

Spirituality and volunteerism have long history to work out for wellbeing of the masses (Okun et al.,2015). There are so many religious organizations which are involved in social service in time of disaster situation in emergency response across the world(Sullivan,2019). Both, agreement and disagreement were reported in previous literature regarding the religious mind related to social service, hence it is very hard to figure out what level of religion has involvement in civic related activities across world (Van et al.,2020; Ilyas et al.,2019; Sullivan,2019). However, large of number of literature figure out that individuals, groups or organizations have linked with any religion advocate regarding the welfare of marginalize segment of population (Sullivan,2019; Yerkes,2019; Riyadi et al.,2021). In term of religion, it was also observed that individuals who engaged in daily religious activities had more active to donate money for needy as compared the individual who had less involvement in religious activities. In addition, the persons who are more involved community development are more likely participate in volunteer to support needy people of community than those who only express high degree of social trust, hence results indicated that religion has significant impact on civic engagement (Diop et al.,2018). By supporting, above argument, literature civically active young as well adolescent came from the religious family background (Balkaya et al.,2020).

Significance of study

In the age of covid19, young generation of developing and developed countries are dealing with post effect of in terms of social as well as economic issues. Lack of physical communication of youth with different proportion of society leads toward stress as well as state of anxiety. During and after pandemic state's institutions were working to help nation in terms of social and economic strain to bring life on normal, however, effects of pandemic were huge, efforts state's institutions were not sufficient. Across world, likeminded people steps up to work for development society by helping in different ways. There are so many factors involved in developed of individual and society including social capital, family support even religion. It is common that social capital is an invisible asset any person while help to link individual as group of people to different social groups to gain and support

people for development of society. Social capital can be used at micro and macro level to deal with issues in hard time without any government institution involvement.

This research assessed the association between social capital, family support and religion and civic engagement. The hypotheses of study were measured using multi-regression. In previous studies, variables of study were used individual level, the current research used to test combine effect of bonding social capital, bridging social capital, family support and religion with civic engagement, it is first major theoretical contribution study while study was conducted in Japanese context, it is second major contextual contribution of current study. The outcomes of current research may contribute in domain research. Current research would be helpful for philanthropist, social workers and development professionals to implement development project to make ease for family who faced financial and social hardship during and after the pandemic and current cyclone post effect. The results of current study may be helpful for new researchers to conduct domain research.

2. Methodology

Research instrument

The most difficult task in the deductive approach is to design a suitable questionnaire according to objectives of study. The vague and lengthy research instrument that consumes a huge amount of time of respondents may lead towards errors, even biasness (Schwarz, Hippler, Deutsch, & Strack, 1985). Regarding the types of scale, especially rating scales, needs more concentration over reliability and validity, however, it is very easy to respond within short time and it is respondent oriented. (Marsden & Wright, 2010). Many types of rating scales were reported in literature (Miller, & Miller, 1977) while Likert scale is widely used in quantitative research. Hence, it is very hard to define that which one is standardized rating scale is. The scale of research instrument varies on the types of questions and variables under the investigation. Types of rating scale support to enhance the reliability and validity results. Therefore, uniqueness of the scales including items cannot be violated. In this research adapted items were applied with small modification while some items were developed according to requirements of the current study.

Dependent variable

In the current study, dependent variable was used civic engagement. For this purpose, the scales were adapted from the 4-study programs, the items were developed to assess social activities in context of youth developed and refined by Bobek et al., (2009). Total items were 9 while reliability of factor level measured .73. The items' scales were rating from 1 = once to 5 = never. The current factor level reliability was reported .82.

Independent variables

The social capital scales were divided into two sections, bonding social capital and bridging social capital. Bonding as well as bridging social both were assessed 5 points Likert scales, with response 1 strongly agree to 5 strongly disagree. A minor modification was made to fix items regarding cultural setting while items were adapted from previous study (Williams, 2006). At the factor level, bonding social capital Cronbach's alpha was .68 while

bridging social capital Cronbach's alpha was a bit better than bonding social capital and reported .78. overall reliability of factors of social capital was at good level as suggested by (Sarstedt et.al., 2017). The bridging social capital was measured with 10 items, adapted from (Williams, 2006). Family support related three items were developed for current study. The assessment of Cronbach's alpha was also faire and report .69 while involvement of religion was assessed with civic engagement in Japanese context. For this purpose, total 4 items were developed, reliability items were less than minimum requirement, it was excluded from study while remaining three items' Cronbach's alpha was .73. Overall reliability of factors level was satisfactory.

Procedure

The current data was collected online using google form and form was linked to different social media plat forms. On the top of questionnaire, basic information related to project and purpose of the study was given along the keynote, data would be confidential and anonymous. At consent note, it was mentioned that any individual participate in study by filling questionnaire would be willing to participate in survey. It was very difficult to figure out the sample size to maximize the representation of undergraduate Japanese students. Appropriate simple size was obtained using G* power software. Data was collected during surge of covid19, hence response rate just faire. During three-month data collecting and three reminders, total 362 questionnaires were received back and was enough for quantitative research in terms multivariate analysis. First, uncompleted forms were sorted out and seven cases in which just demographic variable were filled that contributed just 1.93 proportion of obtained data, hence it was excluded from datasheet. Second, data was cleaned using some statistical tests such as missing values and outliers. Missing values and outliers were dealt properly and hypotheses were tested on final 333 samples.

3. Results

Demographic characteristics of respondents

After cleaning data, study was conducted on final 209 samples. Results of descriptive statistics regarding the demographic characteristics revealed, majority of respondents were male and contributed about (117)56% while female respondents were (99)44%. At the age level, large number of respondents age was 25 to 30 and shared (116)55.5% and second large number of responds age was reported between 20 to25 and contributed 35.9% of total samples and (16)7.7% respondents age was between 31 to 35 years while just (2)1.0%, (31 to 35)7.7%. In term of marital status, large number was reported single, (112) 53.6%, married were (24)11.5. Cohabitated were (71)34% and widow/Divorced (2)1%indentified. At the department level, about (109) 52.2% was related to management science, Social science, (74)35.4 and the students who belonged to natural science, were (26)12.4%.

Internal consistency

The internal consistency of variables was tested through Pearson correlation coefficient.

Table 1 Pearson's correlation coefficient

Factors	Civic engagement	Bonding capital	Bridging capital	Family	Religion
Civic engagement	1				
Bonding capital	.195**	1			
Bridging capital	.119	.219**	1		
Family	.246**	.068	.243**	1	
Religion	.151*	.144*	.321**	.373**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The table 2 figure out the results for H1 and pointing out that it is statistically significant values at $p < 0.05$. The outcome of result support positive and significant impact of bonding social capital on civic youth civic engagement while results for H2 reported that there is no association between bridging social capital and youth civic engagement in Japanese context with value $p > 0.05$. Third H3 was developed to assess the association between family support and civic engagement. The results pointed that there is significant association between family support and youth civic engagement. The current results support agreement, support from family helps to enhance youth social activities in society. The result for H4 also was not different, religion has positive and significant association with youth civic engagement with values $p < 0.05$ which predicted that affiliation of religion can lead toward participate in social activities to support less developed segment of society.

Table 2 Hypothetical Relationship

Factors relationship	Beta	t	p
Bonding capital -----> Civic engagement	.13	1.98	.04
Bridging capital ----->Civic engagement	.05	0.76	.45
Family -----> Civic engagement	.16	2.32	.02
Religion -----> Civic engagement	.19	2.65	.01
R ² =.125			
F=7.26			

4. Discussion

Civic engagement is a basic element which help coordinate people to people performing different social activities. Different types of social activities done enhance social capital among masses where provision of rights of people can be secured easily. The active citizens by performing collective action to reshape society and lead towards prosperity of society. The main purpose current study was to assess the impact of social capital, family support and religion on civic engagement Japanese society. The respondents of study were undergraduate University students. In this model, relationship between social capital, family support and religion have been tested with civic engagement Japanese context.

The results of current study revealed that bonding social capital has positive and significant relationship between civic engagement in Japanese context. Hence H1 accepted. The results of current study collaborate with previous study (Jalalani et al.,2019).

Results illustrated that Japanese generation steps up to support needy people any kind of situation.

Second objective of study was developed to assess the impact of bridging social on civic engagement in Japanese context. For this purpose, H2 was developed. Results showed that there is no positive and significant association between bridging social capital and civic engagement in Japanese context. Hence H2 rejected. Results of current study linked with previous studies (Jalalani et al.,2018; Besser, 2009). In not only, Japanese context but even other context such as in Asian context, bridging social were not found associated with civic engagement. In future research, a suitable mediator must be tested with bridging social capital to link association between bridging social civic engagement.

Family is considered a basic primary institution where from socialization start and reshape personality of individual. Family connection is a major predictor of civic engagement in any society. For assessing the family support to performing social activities in Japanese context H3 was developed. Results figured out that family support positive and significant impact on civic engagement. Hence, H3 accepted. Results of current study is consistent with previous studies (Finn & Momani,2023; Jalalani et al.,2019). Study points that family encourage youth to be active in social activities to help the needy people, young generation steps up to work out for local people.

Religion is considered main indicator which advocates individual to work out for development of masses. To assess impact of religion over social activities, Last hypothesis was developed to assess association between religion and civic engagement in Japanese context. The result of current study has revealed that religion has positive and significant impact on civic engagement. The results of current study linked with (Yuen & Leung,2022; Steenland., et al.,2022). In different societies, spirituality associated with social activities in both level, spirituality at level of civic engagement in terms of discursive and practical level. Actually spirituality has conscious level impact and even implicit means in civic life (Steenland et al., 2022).

5. Conclusion

The current research points out that bonding social has positive association with civic engagement in Japanese context which illustrates that the social primary institutions support their young generation to work out for betterment of society as well as needy people. However, this association was reported Weak in terms of bridging social. This weak relationship figures out that social out groups do not encourage and support individual to steps up work out for betterment of needy people. It may state of has better mechanism to solve issues of masses on propriety basis. In the context of family support, result is very supportive, and find positive and significant. Results of current study figures that that family is system still strong in Japanese society and encourages their youngsters to participate in social activities which help to make easy life for needy people of society. It is because of primary socialization. Religion inspires people to participates social activities However, it depends on level of individual spiritual grow and involvement social activities. In this current research, association of religion was assessed with civic engagement related activities and positive and significant. The result of this research is consistent with previous domain

research (Mayseless & Kizel, 2022). Commonly, individual's spiritual nurturing is not limited in terms of understanding of the individual. Hence, such nurturing mostly enhances towards other circles individual life and directly indirectly influence over choice and behavior be linked with other members of society to steps up for betterment of society.

Current study had several limitations, the current study does not represent whole youths of Japanese society. In future research, focus must be over communities' youth rather than over university students. Furthermore, in time horizon, current study was cross-sectional, may better results can be obtained through longitudinal data. In spite, limitations, current study has very important implications. In theoretical perspectives, results pointed out role of family support and religion both are significant to promote civic engagement through performing social activities for better of society.

6. Reference

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